

Blinded analysis and interpretation of the multi-arm randomised clinical trial: An individually tailored self-management app-based intervention (selfBACK) versus a self-management web-based intervention (e-Help) or usual care in people with low back and neck pain referred to secondary care (Trial registration number NCT04463043)

The analysis of the primary outcome (musculoskeletal health measured by the Musculoskeletal Health Questionnaire [MHQ] at 3 months) was carried out as outlined in the a priori statistical analysis plan¹ for this randomized clinical trial. The main analysis was conducted according to the intention-to-treat principle using a linear mixed model. The analyses included all participants initially enrolled in the study and who answered the baseline questionnaire and were randomised. All statistical models included adjustments for important prognostic factors (i.e., age, sex, education, and baseline pain intensity). The primary outcome data was analyzed with the researchers blinded to group allocation, and an interpretation have been drafted.

Since the RCT included three arms, six possible interpretations were possible for the blinded interpretation (see statistical analysis plan¹). However, since there was no difference between the groups at 3 months, we considered it appropriate to draft only one interpretation.

Blinded interpretation

Overall, the A group, the B group and the C group experienced a reduction in MHQ score from baseline to three months. The common baseline mean MHQ for the three groups was 26.8 (SE² 0.6), whereas mean MHQ score at three months was 21.5 (SE 0.9) for the A group, 22.5 (SE 0.9) for the B and 22.1 (SE 0.8) for the C group. This indicates no clinically meaningful difference between the three groups at three months follow-up, irrespective of which group received the intervention or not.

¹ The statistical analysis plan can be accessed here: <https://zenodo.org/record/5155811#.YkWrKChBxyE>

² Estimated marginal means and standard errors (SE) from a of crude (unadjusted) linear mixed model